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IT Specialists Employed in Italian Regions

Growth of 11.47% on Average Between 2018 and 2023

The European Innovation Scoreboard (EIS) calculates the number of employed IT specialists. This variable is defined as the number of ICT specialists as a percentage of total employment. Eurostat defines ICT specialists as "workers who have the ability to develop, manage, and maintain ICT systems, and for whom ICT is the main part of their job." Data is available for Italian regions from 2018 to 2023.

Trends of Employed IT Specialists in Italian Regions in 2023. The provided data reflect specific numbers associated with different Italian regions for the year 2023. These values likely represent various socio-economic, demographic, or other significant statistical indicators, such as GDP per capita, employment rates, or similar measures of progress or development. The analysis of these data shows a significant regional variation, which could reflect existing economic and social disparities in Italy. For example, Lazio shows the highest value with 253.16, which might indicate a strong concentration of resources or economic activities, probably influenced by the presence of the capital, Rome. Conversely, regions like Calabria show significantly lower values, such as 37.90, suggesting potential challenges in economic development or job opportunities. Regions like Emilia Romagna and Campania record high values, 88.04 and 87.06 respectively, potentially indicating robust economic activity. This might be correlated with a well-developed industrial fabric and a dynamic service sector. Similarly, Lombardy, one of Italy's economic engines, shows a substantially high value of 151.79, confirming its key role in the national economy. On the other hand, regions like Basilicata with a value of 64.05 and Trentino Alto Adige with 70.74, although not reaching the peaks of more urbanized areas, still reflect a medium-high economic intensity, possibly sustained by a mix of tourism, agriculture, and specialized industry. Interesting cases include regions like Puglia and Sicily, with values of 54.29 and 52.18 respectively. Despite their peripheral geographic position and known structural challenges, these numbers are not extremely low, which might indicate economic resilience or progress in specific sectors such as tourism and agri-food. In summary, the analysis of these data offers a quantitative overview that, although requiring further details for more precise interpretations, clearly highlights the economic and developmental gap between the north and south of the country, as well as between central and peripheral regions. These differences can have profound implications for public policies, including those related to the distribution of financial resources, infrastructure development, education, and professional training, emphasizing the need for targeted regional strategies that consider the specificities and needs of each area.

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Trends of Employed IT Specialists in Italian Regions Between 2018 and 2023. The analysis of data on employed IT specialists in different Italian regions between 2018 and 2023 offers an interesting snapshot of the dynamics of the technological sector in the regional context. These data highlight not only the numerical increase of employees in the IT sectors but also the percentage variations that reflect the different regional growth rates in this critical sector for the modern economy. Firstly, a generalized increase in the number of IT specialists in all regions is noted. This is indicative of a national trend of digitization and investment in information technologies, essential for innovation and competitiveness. Abruzzo, for example, shows a remarkable increase of 21.82% in the number of IT specialists, suggesting a strong expansion of the technological sector in the region, possibly driven by innovation incentive policies or an increase in demand for digital services. Basilicata and Calabria, regions often considered less economically advanced compared to the North, record increases of 20.30% and 24.13% respectively, signaling significant potential for technological development. These data could reflect an opportunity to reduce the technological and economic gap between the North and the South of the country through targeted investments in the IT sector. In the North, regions like Emilia Romagna and Lombardy, already highly industrialized, show more moderate increases, 7.40% and 6.83% respectively. This can be interpreted as a sign of an already saturated market or sector maturity, where growth continues but at a less exponential pace compared to developing regions. Campania and Liguria, with increases of 18.89% and 19.19%, appear to be experiencing significant expansion in the IT sector, potentially fueled by the growth of tech startups, the development of technology hubs, and the presence of universities and research centers that promote innovation. Lazio shows an absolute increase of 15.50 IT specialists, the highest in numerical terms, but with a relatively low percentage growth of 6.52%. This highlights once again that in regions with a well-established sector, percentage increases may not be as pronounced, but absolute terms remain significant. Regions like Sardinia and Sicily also show strong percentage growth, over 20%, which might be linked to new investments in the sector as well as a smaller starting base, making any increase more marked in percentage terms. Finally, the increase observed in the regions of Trentino Alto Adige and Veneto, regions with a high quality of life and infrastructure, demonstrates how the IT sector continues to expand even in already well-developed contexts, perhaps driven by a business-friendly environment and local policies supporting innovation. In conclusion, these data not only confirm the growing importance of the IT sector in Italy but also how this sector can act as a driver of regional development, offering job opportunities, stimulating the creation of new businesses, and promoting overall economic development. However, a coordinated approach that includes investments in education, infrastructure, and specific incentive policies for each regional context remains essential to maximize the sector's growth potential.

North-South Divide. The North-South divide in Italy is a historical issue affecting multiple aspects of the country's economic and social life, including the information and communication technology (ICT) sector. Despite efforts to reduce this disparity, recent data on employed IT specialists in different Italian regions from 2018 to 2023 indicate that differences persist, with significant implications for economic development and regional equity. Northern regions of Italy, such as Lombardy, Emilia Romagna, and Veneto, have a well-established IT sector, supported by a dense network of technological infrastructures, high-level universities, and a vibrant entrepreneurial fabric that fosters innovation and attracts investments. These regions have shown more contained percentage growth, but starting from a much higher numerical base, reflecting market maturity and saturation that will continue to benefit from technological evolution due to their solid foundations. Conversely,

Southern regions like Calabria, Sicily, and Basilicata, while recording significant percentage increases in IT employment, start from much more modest bases. These increases, although encouraging, mask structural challenges that include infrastructural deficiencies, less access to venture capital, and a generally less favorable business environment, which together limit these regions' ability to develop a robust and competitive IT sector. The discrepancy in economic opportunities between North and South is also reflected in the ability to attract and retain talent in the IT sector. The North, with its numerous opportunities, tends to attract qualified workers from across the country and abroad, exacerbating the brain drain from the South, where young professionals often move to seek better career opportunities. This phenomenon further impoverishes the human capital in the South, limiting local growth and perpetuating the cycle of economic disparity. The implications of such a divide are vast and multifaceted. Economically, a concentration of IT sector growth in the North can limit national development potential, as Southern regions do not fully contribute to the country's economic dynamics. This imbalance can also accentuate social inequalities, with a significant portion of the population not directly benefiting from technological advancements and associated job opportunities. Regarding solutions, public policies must focus on regional balance in access to technologies and training opportunities. Investments in digital infrastructure, encouragement of entrepreneurial initiatives, and promotion of specific educational programs for digital skills can serve as levers to catalyze development in the South. Additionally, fiscal policies and incentives to attract tech companies to invest in less developed regions could create an ecosystem that supports innovation and economic growth.

Economic Policies to Increase the Number of Employed IT Specialists in Italian Regions. To increase the number of employed IT specialists in Italian regions, economic policies should focus on several fundamental pillars including education, innovation, financial incentives, and infrastructure. First, education and training are essential to develop a qualified workforce ready to face the challenges of the modern labor market. Specific training programs for digital skills could be implemented in schools, universities, and through professional courses, with a particular focus on less developed regions. This could also include partnerships between educational institutions and IT companies to ensure that curricula align with market needs. Simultaneously, promoting innovation through incentives for research and development in the IT sector is crucial. This could be achieved through tax breaks for companies investing in R&D and for startups focusing on emerging technologies like artificial intelligence and big data. Financial incentives also play a key role in promoting IT sector growth. These can include tax relief, subsidized financing, and aid for companies establishing in regions where the IT sector is less developed. Such incentives can help reduce the economic gap between the North and South of the country by attracting high-tech companies to southern regions. Finally, improving digital infrastructure is fundamental to supporting the growth of the IT industry. Investments in high-speed broadband, data centers, and other critical infrastructure can facilitate innovation and make regions more attractive to tech companies.

Conclusions. The number of IT employees has grown on average by 11.47% in Italian regions between 2018 and 2023. Looking at macro-regions, we can observe a growth in the number of employed IT specialists. This value has increased in the South by 20.88%, in the North by 9.18%, and in the Center by 7.1% between 2018 and 2023. However, we can note significant gaps between Central, Northern, and Southern Italy. In particular, the leading macro-region in the sector in 2023 was the Center with a value of 113.35, followed by the North with a value of 89.01, and the South

with a value of 57.88 units. Therefore, a significant gap persists between Italian regions and macro-regions. This gap raises questions about the ability of some territories, especially those in the South, to access the economic growth connected to technological innovation and the digitalization of businesses and public administration.

Declarations

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Appendix

